

UZBEKISTAN IS A SUPPORTER OF OPEN, SYSTEMATIC AND EFFECTIVE DIALOGUE AT THE "CENTRAL ASIA – EUROPEAN UNION" SUMMIT

Sharipov Marat

University: University of World Economy and Diplomacy; Faculty: International Relations;
Major: Political Science; Year: Third;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7313336>

Abstract. This article explains that Uzbekistan is a supporter of open, systematic and effective dialogue at the "Central Asia - European Union" summit. The descriptive analysis method is used as the main method, and the retrospective analysis method is used as an auxiliary method. The subject of research is bilateral relations between Uzbekistan and the European Union, how attention is being paid to such areas as trade, investment, culture, logistics, tourism, regional security as an object of growing cooperation. The purpose of the article is to promote practical cooperation, strengthen trust, partnership and interdependence. As a source for the article, the opinions of various guides were taken from industry representatives.

Keywords: trade, economy, "GSP+" preferential trade, export, partnership, industry, transport-logistics, Trans-Caspian multimodal route, eco-innovations, "green" development.

УЗБЕКИСТАН ЯВЛЯЕТСЯ СТОРОННИКОМ ОТКРЫТОГО, СИСТЕМАТИЧЕСКОГО И ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ДИАЛОГА НА САММИТЕ «ЦЕНТРАЛЬНАЯ АЗИЯ - ЕВРОПЕЙСКИЙ СОЮЗ»

Аннотация. В статье поясняется, что Узбекистан является сторонником открытого, системного и эффективного диалога на саммите «Центральная Азия-Европейский Союз». В качестве основного использовался метод описательного анализа, а в качестве вспомогательного – метод ретроспективного анализа. Предметом исследования являются двусторонние отношения между Узбекистаном и Европейским Союзом, а в качестве объекта растущего сотрудничества – внимание, уделяемое сферам торговли, инвестиций, культуры, логистики, туризма и региональной безопасности. Цель статьи - способствовать практическому сотрудничеству, укреплению доверия, партнерства и взаимозависимости. В качестве источника для статьи были взяты мнения различных гидов от представителей отрасли.

Ключевые слова: торговля, экономика, преференциальная торговля «ВСП+», экспорт, партнерство, промышленность, транспортно-логистический комплекс, Транскаспийский мультимодальный маршрут, экоинновации, «зеленое» развитие.

INTRODUCTION

In particular, after independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan, diplomatic relations with the European Union established in 1994. Also, the Mission of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the European Communities established its activities in Brussels, in 1995, and by 2011, the "European House" in Tashkent was given the status of diplomatic representation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It should be recognized that important meetings have been organized between the European Union and Uzbekistan in the past 27 years. These have been a great reason for the political level meetings, to improve focusing foreign trade, investment, regional security, ecology, energy, transport, logistics, tourism, cultural, and educational spheres in bilateral relations between the countries. One of the high-level meetings in 2017 y. and 2019 y. were

between President Shavkat Mirziyoyev and Federica Mogherini, Donald Tusk, which gained historical significance.

The reputation of our country at the international level is increasing, and it is of particular importance as it serves the development of our economy, the well-being of our people, and the prospects of our country. Therefore, the participation of the head of our state Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the first "Central Asia - European Union" summit held in Astana, and in his speech he touched on the trade and economic direction of the cooperation between our region and the European Union, and added our countries to the "GSP+" preferential trade system. A clear example of this is the fact that the export of Uzbek products with high added value has almost doubled since the beginning of this year.

At this summit, which was attended by the Presidents of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and the Council of Europe, as well as the Deputy Chairman of the Cabinet of Ministers of Turkmenistan, the President said that this format is necessary for promoting practical cooperation, strengthening trust, partnership and interdependence. specially recognized that it is considered as an important area of dialogue.

“We are not resting on our laurels and intend to increase the scale of transformations. First of all, we are talking about the unconditional rule of law, all-round support for civil society institutions, ensuring human rights and gender equality, freedom of speech and religion”, Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized.[1]

RESULTS

In order to adequately compete with the nomenclature of finished, non-raw goods in European markets:

- Securing and guaranteeing compliance of mechanical items with tall European guidelines and specialized directions;
- Creation of the most optimal and efficient transport and logistics corridors for access to the markets of the Republic of Belarus, first of all, the development of the Trans-Caspian multimodal route;
- Underlining the need to conduct joint marketing research and targeted events and promotions for the recognition and purchase of products from Central Asian countries among European consumers, establishing the "European Union - Central Asia" Economic Cooperation Committee at the level of Deputy Prime Ministers to systematically solve these issues was offered.

That's what matter in foreign affairs, the key region of participation is to guarantee territorial security. Shavkat Mirziyoyev supported help of the European Union inside the system of joint programs to combat fear mongering, radicalism, extremism and terrorism, drug trafficking and other crimes.

Another key point, government of Uzbekistan focused on the importance of strengthening practical cooperation in ensuring regional security. In particular, the need for coordinated action and real support of the entire international community in the issue of assistance to Afghanistan was shown. After the adoption of the updated strategy of the European Union for Central Asia, it was noted that many activities and issues were not fully implemented due to the pandemic.

As Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, “as a result of joint efforts, a completely new political atmosphere has formed in Central Asia. In a few years, many problems that had been accumulating for decades, in the solution of which practically no one believed, were resolved.

Today the situation has changed dramatically. A visa-free regime has been introduced, all checkpoints are open. The frequency of flights and ground transportation has increased". [1]

Moreover, specific consideration was paid to encourage relation of great neighborliness and territorial association. The closeness of the sees of the parties on the issue of the Afghan settlement was noted. Uzbekistan routinely gives compassionate help to the Afghan individuals, does not halt the supply of power, oil items and nourishment, does not halt the travel of goods through our nation within the heading of Afghanistan. The status to proceed productive participation with European accomplices in utilizing the potential of coordinations and logistics in our border city of Termez was demonstrated.

Coming from international practise, it was proposed that to set up participation between our uncommon administrations and law requirement organizations to trade data and mutually counter present day dangers.

Regarding the economy, it was pointed that within the financial measurement, the foremost favorable conditions for business people will proceed to be made, an uncompromising battle against corruption will proceed, and the improvement of a competitive and imaginative commerce environment in market will be empowered. Agreeable ties are being reinforced, joint speculation companies and other money related rebellious for the execution of expansive ventures have been made.

Similarly, the enormous potential in tourism and advertised to organize a introduction for the driving European administrators of the concept of a common territorial tourism item amid the primary EU-Central Asia Tourism Gathering in Khiva following year.

It is known that in the second half of November of this year, a large exhibition dedicated to the culture of the peoples of our region will be organized in the Louvre Museum in Paris. The importance of holding such events annually in the capitals and cultural centers of European countries was mentioned. The most gratifying thing is that the leader of our country emphasized that he is a supporter of open, systematic and fruitful dialogue in the format of "Central Asia - European Union" for the sustainable development, prosperity and well-being of our countries.

DISCUSSION

Another key fact to remember, the European Union to activate cooperation in the field of "green" development, paying special attention to eco-innovations, wide introduction of energy-efficient and resource-saving technologies, digitization of economic sectors, "smart" agriculture with the help of the European network "Smart-AKIS" programme that focus on the development of the country.

The President of our nation pointed that "the worldwide and territorial circumstance has profoundly changed, which nowadays requires more dynamic bolster by European accomplices of the integration forms in Central Asia." [1] In this respect, it was proposed to consider the plausibility of embracing a multilateral program report – a "road map" to quicken the execution of the European Union Procedure for Central Asia" and fortify partnerships. Confidence was communicated that these issues will be substantively considered amid the up and coming joint Ministerial Conference on Interconnectivity, which can be held following month in Samarkand.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that the rational foreign policy conducted by our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev brings New Uzbekistan closer to the world, creates the ground for stabilization with the world economy and to be mentioned among the economically developed

countries. It was emphasized once again that the "European Union - Central Asia" format is a supporter of open, systematic and effective dialogue.

REFERENCES

1. https://uzbekembassy.com.my/eng/news_press/address_by_the_president_of_uzbekistan_shavkat_mirziyoyev_at_first_central_asia_european_union_summit.html.
2. M.T. Laumulin, "The EU and Central Asia: The View from Central Asia," *Central Asia's Affairs*, No. 4, 2009, pp. 20-24; idem, "Central Asia in the Foreign Policy Strategy of the European Union," in: *New Europe (Brussels), Special Report: Kazakhstan*, No. 878, 2010, pp. 20-21.
3. G.K. Kydyrkhanova, *Borba s narkotrafikom i mezhdunarodnym terrorizmom v sotrudnichestve stran Tsentralnoy Azii i Evropeyskogo soiuza*, KazNU, Almaty, 2009, 121 pp.
4. M. Emerson, J. Boonstra, N. Hasanova, M. Laruelle, S. Peyrouse, op. cit., p. 111.
5. Kh. Inomjonov, "Otnosheniia Uzbekistana s Evropeyskim soiuзом," *Tsentralnaia Azia: vneshniy vzgliad*, pp. 464-486.
6. M. Laumilin, "Vneshniaia politika Uzbekistana na sovremnom etape," *Kazakhstan v globalnykh protsessakh*, No. 1, 2010, pp. 56-72.